

δ 4.9 (1H, t) and 2.5 (1H, m) established the presence of protons at C-5 and C-1 respectively. A complicated pattern in the range δ 6.8–8.8 (7.5) showed the presence of ten aromatic protons. The mass spectrum of 2 gave a molecular ion peak at M^+ 300. Other characteristic peaks were obtained at m/z 299, 284, 270, 269, 268, 254, 253, 239, 208, 179, 157 and 36 (base peak).

2.HCl (in a solution of propylene glycol) was subjected to preliminary pharmacological screening on albino mice (15–20 g) of either sex. Its LD_{50} value was 316.24 mg/kg i.p., with significant CNS depressant activity.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected 1H nmr spectrum was recorded on a EM-390 (90 MHz) spectrophotometer and mass spectrum on a Hitachi-RMu-6EL spectrometer. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc using silica gel-G and benzene–ethanol–ammonia (7 : 2 : 1, v/v).

2-Benzyl-1-ethyl-1,2-dihydro-benzo[f]quinoline (1) : Freshly prepared benzylmagnesium chloride (7.56 g benzyl chloride and 1.44 g magnesium) was slowly added to benzo[f]quinolinium ethiodide (13.4 g) with continuous stirring for 3 h at 40–50°. After refluxing, the mixture was poured onto crushed ice (100 g) containing NH_4Cl (10 g) and concentrated HCl (10 ml). It was then basified with NH_4OH and extracted with ether (250 ml). The ether extract was dehydrated (Na_2SO_4) and concentrated to afford an oil which on distillation at 160° (0.2 mm) gave 1 (3.22 g, 27%); 1.HCl, m.p. 205° (Found: N, 4.48. $C_{21}H_{21}N.HCl$ requires: N, 4.32%); recrystallised from acetone–petroleum ether (1 : 4).

2-N-Ethyl-(3,4-a)naphtho-6,7-benzomorphan (2) : A mixture of 1 (3.6 g) and 85% H_3PO_4 (30 ml) was refluxed for 48 h at 140°. It was then poured onto crushed ice (100 g) basified with NH_4OH and extracted with ether (250 ml). Concentration of the ethereal layer afforded an oil which was distilled at 180° (0.2 mm) to give 2 (1.50 g, 42%); 2.HCl m.p. 125° (Found: C, 77.80; H, 6.92. $C_{21}H_{21}N.HCl$ requires: C, 77.59; H, 6.80).

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Synthesis of Indeno[2,1-c]isocoumarins and Indeno[2,1-c]isoquinolones. Part-II

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THE indenoisocoumarins have an unsaturated β -lactone ring in the isocoumarin moiety and hence may be expected to exhibit physiological properties. Chatterjea and Mukherjee^{1,2} reported the synthesis of a few indenoisocoumarins (5) by heating α -benzylhomophthalic acids (2) with commercial PPA. Compounds 2 in turn were obtained by the interaction of benzaldehydes with dimethyl homophthalate in the presence of sodium methoxide followed by saponification of the resulting product and subsequent sodium amalgam reduction of α -benzylidene homophthalic acids (1). In an alternative route these authors¹ carried out the Stobbe condensation of *o*-carboxybenzaldehydes with diethyl homophthalates followed by reduction of the resulting *o*-carboxy- α -benzylidenehomophthalic acid (3) as usual to *o*-carboxy- α -benzylhomophthalic acids (4), which when heated with Ac_2O gave indeno[1,2-c]isocoumarins (5). These syntheses involve a number of steps and consequently the yield of indenoisocoumarins was always low.

NOTES

Jha and Srivastava⁸ explored a new route to the synthesis of indenoisocoumarins. The method involves the reaction of the highly reactive 2-bromoindan-1-one (6) with substituted-benzoic acid (7) to give 1-oxo-2-indanyl benzoate (8) in ethanolic solution at pH 6.5. Cyclodehydration in presence of H₂SO₄ (90%) or PPA of 8 gives indeno[2,1-*c*]-isocoumarin (9).

To establish the general applicability of this newly developed route, eight new indenoisocoumarins (8a-h) have now been prepared.

The 1-oxo-2-indanyl benzoates (7a-h; Table 1) were prepared by the reactions of benzoic acids (11a-d) with indan-1-ones (10a-b). These esters were characterised through the preparation of their 2,4-DNP derivatives.

The esters (12a-h) underwent cyclodehydration in the presence of H₂SO₄ (90%) to give the corresponding indeno[2,1-*c*]isocoumarins (13a-h; Table 2). Their structural assignment were based on elemental analyses, uv, ir, mass and nmr spectral data. Conversion of 12 to 13 could also be brought about by PPA.

The isocoumarins (13a-h) on treatment with liquor ammonia aniline, ethylamine, *o*-toluidine, *p*-toluidine and α -naphthylamine separately in ethanol, furnished the corresponding indeno[2,1-*c*]isocoumarin-5-(6*H*)-ones (14; Table 3).

10a; R=R¹=H, R²=R³=OMe
 10b; R²=OMe, R=R¹=R³=H
 11a; R¹=R²=OMe, R=R³=H
 11b; R¹=OMe, R=R²=R³=H
 11c; R=R²=OMe, R¹=R³=H
 11d; R¹=R²=OMe, R=R³=H

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF INDANYL BENZOATES (12)*

Compd. no.	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol formula	$[\alpha]_D^{20}$ (CHCl ₃)	λ_{max} (EtOH) nm	ν_{max} (KBr) cm ⁻¹	δ (80 MHz) (ODCl ₂)
12a	57	140-42 ^a	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₇	-88.5°	270, 322	1 730, 1 705	3.6 (2H, m, OH ₂), 3.85, 4.0 (each 6H, s, OCH ₃), 5.7 (1H, t, -CO-H), 6.7-7.0 (8H, m, Ar H-4, H-6 and H-7'), 7.3 (2H, m, Ar H-2 and H-6)
12b	66	148-49 ^b	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₆	-99.5°	265, 320	1 735, 1 705	3.65 (2H, m, OH ₂), 3.9, 3.95, 4.0 (each 3H, s, OCH ₃), 5.6 (1H, t, -CO-H), 6.6-6.9 (4H, m, Ar H-4, H-5, H-6' and H-7'), 7.2, 7.5 (2H, m, Ar H-2 and H-6)
12c	50	146-47 ^b	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₇	-96°	270, 320	1 720, 1 700	3.5 (2H, m, OH ₂), 3.8, 3.85 (each 6H, s, OCH ₃), 5.6 (1H, t, -CO-H), 6.9-7.1 (4H, m, Ar H-3, H-4, H-6 and H-7'), 7.2 (1H, m, Ar H-6)
12d	71	169-70 ^a	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₇	-84°	275, 325	1 724, 1 710	3.6 (2H, m, OH ₂), 3.85, 4.0 (each 6H, s, OCH ₃), 5.5 (1H, t, CHO), 6.7-7.0 (8H, m, Ar H-5, H-6' and H-7'), 7.2, 7.3 (2H, m, Ar H-2 and H-6)
12e	72	120-22 ^a	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₆	-107.5°	260, 315	1 735, 1 710	3.7 (2H, m, OH ₂), 4.0, 4.2, 4.3 (each 3H, s, OCH ₃), 5.8 (1H, t, CHO), 6.7-6.9 (4H, m, Ar H-4, H-4', H-6' and H-7'), 7.4, 7.45 (2H, m, Ar H-2 and H-6)
12f	86.6	127-28 ^b	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₆	-117.5°	265, 315	1 730, 1 700	3.5 (2H, m, OH ₂), 3.7, 3.75 (each 3H, s, OCH ₃), 5.5 (1H, t, CHO), 6.8-7.0 (5H, m, Ar H-4, H-5, H-4', H-6' and H-7'), 7.2 (2H, m, Ar H-2 and H-6)

(Table 1 contd.)

12g	65	148-50 ^b	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₆	-112°	270, 320	1 735, 1 705	3.8 (2H, m, OH ₂), 3.8, 3.9, 3.95 (each 3H, s, OH ₂), 5.7 (1H, t, CHO), 6.9-7.1 (5H, m, Ar H-3, H-4, H-4', H-6' and H-7'), 7.25 (1H, m, Ar H-6)
12h	66	142-43 ^a	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₆	-108°	265, 320	1 725, 1 705	3.60 (2H, m, OH ₂), 3.85, 3.9, 4.0 (each 3H, s, OCH ₃), 5.7 (1H, t, CHO), 6.7-7.0 (4H, m, Ar H-5, H-4', H-6' and H-7'), 7.3, 7.4 (2H, m, Ar H-2 and H-8)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses. **Solvent for crystallisation : ^aEtOH, ^bEtOH - EtOAc

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF INDENO[2,1-c]ISOCOUMARINS (13)*

Compd. no.	Yield %	M.p.** °C	Mol. formula	λ _{max} (EtOH) nm	ν _{max} (KBr) cm ⁻¹	δ (60 MHz) (CDCl ₃)	m/e (relative intensity)
13a	53	188-84 ^a	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₆	265, 330	1 715, 1 695	3.9, 4.0 (each 6H, s, OCH ₃), 4.6 (2H, m, OH ₂), 6.7-6.9 (3H, s, Ar H-6, H-7 and H-9), 7.1 (1H, s, Ar H-11)	354 (100), 326 (9), 312 (14.6), 311 (24), 295 (11), 207 (2.5), 206 (2), 178 (7.25), 166 (19.5), 165 (69.5)
13b	50	137-38 ^b	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₆	270, 332	1 710, 1 695	3.75, 3.8, 3.85 (each 3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.5 (2H, m, OH ₂), 6.8-7.1 (4H, m, Ar H-6, H-7, H-8 and H-9), 7.4 (1H, s, Ar H-11)	324 (100), 296 (9.5), 288 (10.5), 282 (24.75), 265 (12), 177 (3), 176 (4), 148 (6), 136 (12.5), 135 (67.5)
13c	60	133-34 ^b	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₆	275, 335	1 720, 1 705	3.8, 3.85 (each 6H, s, OCH ₃), 4.5 (2H, m, OH ₂), 6.6-6.7 (2H, s, Ar H-6 and H-7), 7.0 (2H, s, Ar H-9 and H-10)	354 (100), 326 (8), 312 (15), 311 (25), 295 (12), 207 (2), 206 (3), 178 (8), 166 (12), 165 (68)
13d	75	186-87 ^a	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₆	270, 340	1 710, 1 698	3.7, 3.8 (each 6H, s, OCH ₃), 4.5 (2H, m, OH ₂), 6.6-6.8 (3H, s, Ar H-6, H-7 and H-8), 7.1 (1H, s, Ar H-11)	354 (100), 326 (8.5), 312 (16), 311 (23), 295 (10), 207 (8), 206 (4), 178 (9), 166 (14), 165 (67.5)
13e	60	132-33 ^a	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₆	270, 330	1 705, 1 695	3.85, 3.9, 3.95 (each 3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.6 (2H, m, OH ₂), 6.8-7.1 (4H, Ar H-4, H-6, H-7 and H-9), 7.3 (1H, s, Ar H-11)	324 (100), 296 (8), 288 (11), 282 (25), 265 (13), 207 (2.5), 206 (2), 178 (8), 166 (12), 165 (68.5)
13f	65	145-46 ^b	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₆	280, 315	1 720, 1 695	3.85, 3.9 (each 3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.5 (2H, m, OH ₂), 6.8, 7.0 (5H, m, Ar H-4, H-6, H-7, H-8 and H-9), 7.4 (1H, m, Ar H-11)	294 (100), 266 (8), 253 (10), 252 (24), 235 (15), 177 (4), 176 (3), 148 (6), 136 (11), 135 (67.5)
13g	60	167-68 ^b	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₆	285, 315	1 720, 1 695	3.9, 3.95, 4.0 (each 3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.6 (2H, m, OH ₂), 6.7-7.0 (3H, m, Ar H-4, H-6 and H-9), 7.3, 7.4 (2H, s, Ar H-7 and H-10)	324 (100), 296 (7), 288 (12), 282 (24), 265 (14), 207 (3), 206 (2), 178 (7), 166 (13), 165 (69)
13h	55	150-58 ^b	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₆	260, 320	1 710, 1 700	3.85, 3.9, 4.0 (each 3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.5 (2H, m, OH ₂), 6.8-7.0 (4H, m, Ar H-4, H-6, H-7 and H-8), 7.5 (1H, m, Ar H-11)	324 (100), 296 (9), 288 (13), 282 (25), 265 (12), 207 (4), 206 (3), 178 (9), 166 (14), 165 (67)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses. **Solvent for crystallisation : ^aEtOH, ^bEtOH - EtOAc

NOTES

TABLE 3—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF INDENO[2,1-c]ISOQUINOLIN-5(6H)-ONES (15)*

Sl. no.	R'	Yield %	M.p.** °C	Mol. formula	λ_{max} (EtOH) nm	ν_{max} (KBr) cm^{-1}	δ (60 MHz) (CDCl ₃)
$R^1=R^2=R^3=R^4=OMe, R^5=R^6=H$							
1.	H	60	233-34 ^a	C ₂₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ N	275, 310	3 315, 2 930, 1 680, 1 585, 1 455, 1 380, 1 340, 1 270, 1 230	3.85, 3.9 (each 6H, s, OCH ₃), 4.5 (2H, m, OH ₂), 6.8-7.0 (3H, m, Ar H-6, H-7 and H-9), 7.2 (1H, s, Ar H-11), 8.9 (1H, s, sec N-H-2)
2.	C ₆ H ₅	50	186-37 ^b	C ₂₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ N	270, 305	2 935, 1 665, 1 590, 1 475, 1 380, 1 330, 1 260, 1 225	3.8, 3.85 (each 6H, s, OCH ₃), 4.55 (2H, m, OH ₂), 6.5-6.8 (3H, m, Ar H-6, H-7 and H-9), 7.1 (1H, s, Ar H-11), 8.1-8.3 (5H, m, Ar H-2', H-3', H-4', H-5' and H-6')
3.	C ₆ H ₅	50	146-47 ^b	C ₂₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ N	270, 320	2 940, 1 660, 1 606, 1 470, 1 370, 1 335, 1 255, 1 240	3.8, 3.9 (each 6H, s, OCH ₃), 4.6 (2H, m, OH ₂), 6.7-6.9 (3H, m, Ar H-6, H-7 and H-9), 7.0 (1H, s, Ar H-11), 1.0 (3H, t, CH ₃ -2'), 1.5 (2H, q, CH ₂ -1')
4.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	50	127-28 ^b	C ₂₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ N	275, 315	2 925, 1 668, 1 590, 1 445, 1 380, 1 355, 1 325, 1 265, 1 235	3.9, 3.95 (each 6H, s, OCH ₃), 4.5 (2H, m, OH ₂), 6.8-7.1 (3H, m, Ar H-6, H-7 and H-9), 7.1 (1H, s, Ar H-11), 8.0-8.2 (4H, m, Ar H-3', H-4', H-5' and H-6'), 2.4 (3H, s, CH ₃ -2')
5.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	60	220-22 ^a	C ₂₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ N	270, 320	2 940, 1 670, 1 595, 1 470, 1 380, 1 335, 1 245, 1 240	3.8, 3.9 (each 6H, s, OCH ₃), 4.6 (2H, m, OH ₂), 6.7-7.0 (3H, m, Ar H-6, H-7 and H-9), 7.2 (1H, s, Ar H-11), 8.1-8.4 (4H, m, Ar H-2', H-3', H-5' and H-6'), 2.3 (3H, s, CH ₃ -4')
6.	α -C ₁₀ H ₇	70	213-15 ^a	C ₃₀ H ₁₈ O ₂ N	265, 325	2 935, 1 667, 1 580, 1 475, 1 385, 1 340, 1 265, 1 235	3.8, 3.85 (each 6H, s, OCH ₃), 4.65 (2H, m, OH ₂), 6.6-6.9 (3H, m, Ar H-6, H-7 and H-9), 7.15 (1H, s, Ar H-11), 8.2-8.5 (7H, m, Ar H-2', H-3', H-4', H-5', H-6', H-7' and H-8')
$R^1=R^2=R^3=OMe, R^4=R^5=R^6=H$							
7.	H	50	166-67 ^a	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₂ N	275, 310	—	—
8.	C ₆ H ₅	50	112-13 ^a	C ₂₅ H ₁₄ O ₂ N	275, 305	—	—
9.	C ₆ H ₅	55	196-97 ^a	C ₂₅ H ₁₄ O ₂ N	280, 315	—	—
10.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	60	202-03 ^a	C ₂₆ H ₁₂ O ₂ N	265, 320	—	—
11.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	50	198-99 ^a	C ₂₆ H ₁₂ O ₂ N	270, 330	—	—
12.	α -C ₁₀ H ₇	70	221-23 ^b	C ₂₉ H ₁₄ O ₂ N	275, 330	—	—
$R^1=R^2=R^3=R^4=OMe, R^5=R^6=H$							
13.	H	50	250-52 ^a	C ₂₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ N	275, 335	—	—
14.	C ₆ H ₅	50	237-38 ^a	C ₂₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ N	265, 330	—	—
15.	C ₆ H ₅	56	195-98 ^a	C ₂₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ N	270, 330	—	—
16.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	65	175-79 ^a	C ₂₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ N	265, 330	—	—
17.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	40	215-19 ^a	C ₂₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ N	260, 315	—	—
18.	α -C ₁₀ H ₇	50	217-18 ^a	C ₃₀ H ₁₈ O ₂ N	270, 305	—	—

(Table 3 contd.)

R ¹ =R ² =R ⁴ =R ⁵ =OMe, R ³ =R ⁶ =H						
19.	H	60	225-27 ^a	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₅ N	270, 315	—
20.	C ₆ H ₅	58	214-15 ^a	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ O ₅ N	275, 320	—
21.	C ₈ H ₇	50	204-06 ^b	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ O ₅ N	270, 330	—
22.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	50	208-09 ^c	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₅ N	265, 320	—
23.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	40	196-97 ^a	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₅ N	260, 320	—
24.	α -C ₁₀ H ₇	60	236-37 ^c	C ₃₀ H ₂₉ O ₅ N	270, 325	—
R ² =R ³ =R ⁵ =OMe, R ¹ =R ⁴ =R ⁶ =H						
25.	H	60	158-60 ^a	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₄ N	276, 310	—
26.	C ₆ H ₅	50	180-81 ^b	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ O ₄ N	275, 310	—
27.	C ₈ H ₇	50	188-90 ^a	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₄ N	278, 312	—
28.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	40	196-98 ^b	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ N	265, 328	—
29.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	60	198-94 ^b	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ N	268, 328	—
30.	α -C ₁₀ H ₇	50	208-09 ^a	C ₃₀ H ₂₉ O ₄ N	274, 330	—
R ² =R ³ =OMe, R ¹ =R ⁴ =R ⁵ =R ⁶ =H						
31.	H	60	167-69 ^a	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₃ N	270, 315	—
32.	C ₆ H ₅	65	167-69 ^b	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ O ₃ N	270, 315	—
33.	C ₈ H ₇	70	172-73 ^a	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₃ N	270, 315	—
34.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	55	204-05 ^a	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₃ N	270, 325	—
35.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	60	179-80 ^a	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₃ N	275, 330	—
36.	α -C ₁₀ H ₇	50	230-32 ^b	C ₃₀ H ₂₉ O ₃ N	275, 325	—
R ³ =R ⁴ =R ⁵ =OMe, R ¹ =R ² =R ⁶ =H						
37.	H	50	155-57 ^b	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₄ N	274, 308	—
38.	C ₆ H ₅	45	99-100 ^a	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ O ₄ N	273, 303	—
39.	C ₈ H ₇	55	184-85 ^a	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₄ N	276, 315	—
40.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	55	190-92 ^a	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ N	265, 318	—
41.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	45	189-90 ^a	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ N	268, 328	—
42.	α -C ₁₀ H ₇	70	205-06 ^a	C ₃₀ H ₂₉ O ₄ N	272, 330	—
R ³ =R ⁴ =R ⁵ =OMe, R ¹ =R ² =R ⁶ =H						
43.	H	60	160-63 ^c	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₄ N	268, 315	—
44.	C ₆ H ₅	50	174-76 ^a	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ O ₄ N	270, 320	—
45.	C ₈ H ₇	50	168-69 ^a	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₄ N	272, 315	—
46.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	55	197-99 ^c	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ N	275, 330	—
47.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	65	174-76 ^c	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ N	273, 323	—
48.	α -C ₁₀ H ₇	50	245-47 ^a	C ₃₀ H ₂₉ O ₄ N	273, 323	—

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses. **Solvent for crystallisation: ^aEtOH, ^bEtOAc, ^cEtOH-EtOAc.

12, 13a; $R^1=R^2=R^3=R^4=OMe$, $R^5=R^6=H$
 12, 13b; $R^1=R^2=R^3=OMe$, $R^4=R^5=R^6=H$
 12, 13c; $R^1=R^2=R^3=R^4=OMe$, $R^5=R^6=H$
 12, 13d; $R^1=R^2=R^3=R^4=OMe$, $R^5=R^6=H$
 12, 13e; $R^1=R^2=R^3=OMe$, $R^4=R^5=R^6=H$
 12, 13f; $R^1=R^2=OMe$, $R^3=R^4=R^5=R^6=H$
 12, 13g; $R^1=R^2=R^3=OMe$, $R^4=R^5=R^6=H$
 12, 13h; $R^1=R^2=R^3=OMe$, $R^4=R^5=R^6=H$

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The uv spectra were recorded on a Beckmann DK-2A spectrophotometer, ir spectra (KBr) on Perkin-Elmer 577, Perkin-Elmer 720 and Beckmann ir-20 spectrophotometers, nmr spectra ($CCl_4/CDCl_3$) on a Varian A-60 spectrometer with TMS as internal standard, and mass spectra on a JEOL D-300 spectrometer. Specific rotation was determined on polarimeter in $CHCl_3$.

1-Oxo-2-indanylbenzoates (12a-h): To an ethanolic solution of 11 (0.01–0.02 mol) which was dropwise neutralised with aqueous sodium hydroxide (5%) till pH 6.5, was added on ethanolic solution of 10 (0.01–0.02 mol) in one lot, and the reaction mixture refluxed on a water-bath for 8 h and then cooled. The resulting solid was filtered and the filtrate concentrated to a solid residue. The two solid residues were mixed together, treated with a saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate, washed with water and crystallised from an appropriate solvent to give 12 (Table 1). The 2,4-DNP derivatives of 12a–h were prepared in the usual way.

Indeno[2,1-c]isocoumarins (13a-h): The ester (12a–h; 0.01 mol) was added in small lots to concentrated H_2SO_4 (15 ml; 90%) at 0–5°, care being taken to add the fresh lot only when the previous one had gone into solution. It was stirred for 3 h at 0–5° and left at room temperature for 40–50 h. The resulting deep red or deep green solution was poured over crushed ice, and the precipitated solid

was treated with a saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate, washed with water, dried and crystallised from a suitable solvent to give 13 (Table 2) as pale yellow to deep brown crystals.

Indeno[2,1-c]isoquinolin-5(6H)-ones (14): A solution of 13 (0.005 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed with liquor ammonia, aniline, ethylamine, *o*-toluidine, *p*-toluidine and α -naphthylamine for 4–6 h on a steam-bath and left overnight. Ethanol was then removed on a steam-bath, followed by removal of excess amine. The residue was filtered, thoroughly washed with a little HCl and water, dried and crystallised from an appropriate solvent to give 14 (Table 3).

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Synthesis of Bis(1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-5-arylhydrazones

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MANY 2-substituted-amino derivatives of 1,3,4-oxadiazole possess various biological activities¹. Some bis-1,3,4-oxadiazoles are also reported as antimicrobial agents^{2,3}. Moreover, some Schiff bases of 1,3,4-oxadiazoles have also shown remarkable antibacterial and antifungal activities⁴. All these facts led us to study the synthesis and antimicrobial activity of the title compounds. The compounds were prepared according to the sequence of reactions outlined in Scheme 1.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. Structures of the compounds were established on the basis of their elemental analysis, m.m.p. and ir spectra. The ir spectra of the compounds showing characteristic bands at 1 280 (N–N=C), 1 500 (conjugated cyclic system C=N), 1 620 (C=N), 1 120 (C–O–C ether linkage), 3 340 (NH) and 820 cm^{-1} (disubstituted benzene), supported the validity of the compounds.

The starting material dihydrazide (1) was prepared by the reaction of hydrazine hydrate on diethyl oxalate⁵.